

Platelet C3G: a key player in vesicle exocytosis, spreading and clot retraction

Running title: C3G regulates platelet secretion and spreading

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Supplemental Tables

Table S1. Sequence of primers used in qPCR (5' to 3'). The canonical names of the genes studied are indicated.

Target	Forward	Reverse
<i>RapGEF1</i>	GTGAGCAAAGAGGCAAGAGA	CACAGCACTGGTG GACATAA
<i>Actb</i>	TAGACTTCGAGCAGGAGATGG	CAAGAAGGAAGGCTGGAAAG
<i>Itgba2-1</i>	AGCCCGTGATCTTTCTAAAC	GCAGCCACAGAGTAACCTAAA
<i>Itgba2-2</i>	CAGTGAGAGCCAAGAAACAAAC	TGTTGGTGGATCGGGTTAAG
<i>Itga2b-1</i>	CTCAACCGAGACGGCTATAATG	CTTCACTCTGACCCAGGAATATC
<i>Itga2b-2</i>	GGCTTCTCAGTGGACTTTCATA	TCTCCTCTTGACTTGCGTTTAG
<i>Itga6-1</i>	GGTTGTGGAACAGCACATTTTC	GCGTGAGGGAGCTTGATATT
<i>Itga6-2</i>	ACTCAGGGAAGGGTATTGTTTC	GTGCGGACTTCATGTCTCTT
<i>ItgaV-1</i>	AGAAGACGTTGGGCCTATTG	TGTAAGGCCACTGGAGATTTAG
<i>ItgaV-2</i>	TTGGCTGCTGTGGAGATAAG	GTCTTCTTCAGTCTCAGGGTTT
<i>ItgaL-1</i>	GCCTATCCTGAGACCTTCAATC	AGGTTTGCCTCACACTTCTT
<i>ItgaL-2</i>	CCACAGACTGCAGAACAGAA	GTTGATGGCACGAAAGGTATTG
<i>Itgb1-1</i>	GACAGTGTGTGTGTAGGAAGAG	GCCTCCACAAATTAAGCCATTAG
<i>Itgb1-2</i>	CAGGTGTCGTGTTTGTGAATG	GATCTGACCATTTGACGCTAGA
<i>Itgb2-1</i>	GTGGTAGGTGTCGTA CTGATTG	GGGACTTGAGTTTCTCCTTCTC
<i>Itgb2-2</i>	GCAGTAATGGAGCATCGAGTAT	TCGGAAGCCATGACCTTTAC
<i>Itgb3-1</i>	GAAGGAGTGTGTGGAGTGTAAG	CTCTTTCACCTGCTCGATGT
<i>Itgb3-2</i>	GCTCATCTGGAAGCTACTCATC	GTGGAGGTGGCCTCTTTATAC
<i>Selp</i>	CTCCTGGCTCTGCTAAGAAAG	GCGTTAGTGAAGACTCCGTATG
<i>Snap23</i>	CAGCCAGTGGTGGATACATT	CCAGAGCCATGTTCTTTAGGT
<i>Stx11</i>	AACCAGCTGCTTCTGATAGAC	AGTTGGTGTGCGCGTTAAT
<i>Stxbp2</i>	CACGCTCACAGCTACTCATAAT	GTCCTGTTTCGATGTCCAGAAG
<i>VAMP-3</i>	AAGCTCTCGGAGCTAGATGA	TCTTGCAGTTCTTCCACCAATA
<i>VAMP-7</i>	GCTTGGTGTGGAGGAAACT	TCCTGTCTTGGCAGATGTATT
<i>VAMP-8</i>	CAGAATGTGGAGCGGATCTT	CTGGGACGTTGTCTTGAAGT

Table S2. Antibodies used for flow cytometry, confocal fluorescence microscopy, immunoprecipitation, and western blot.

Antibody	Vendor or Source	Catalog #	Working concentration
Flow cytometry			
FITC Anti-Mouse CD41 (MWRReg30 clone)	eBiosciences	11-0411-82	1:50
PE Anti-Mouse CD61 (2C9.G3 clone)	eBiosciences	12-0611-81	1:50
APC Anti-Mouse CD41	eBiosciences	17-0411-82	1:100
FITC Anti-Mouse CD62P	BD Pharmigen	553744	1:30
PE- Anti-Mouse α IIb β 3 (JON/A clone)	Emfret	M023-2	1:30
APC Anti-Mouse CD63	BioLegend	143906	1:100
FITC Anti-GPIalpha (CD42b)	Emfret Analytics	M040-1	1:50
FITC Anti-Mouse GPVI	Emfret Analytics	M011-1	1:50
APC Annexin V	BD Pharmigen	550474	1:20
Phalloidin-iFluor 488 Reagent	Abcam	ab176753	1:3000
Confocal immunofluorescence microscopy			
Primary			
C3G (G-4)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-17840	1:100

P-selectin (C-20)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-6941	1:100
SYBL1 (158.2) (VAMP-7)	Abcam	ab36195	1:100
TI-VAMP (H-55) (VAMP-7)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-67060	1:200
Endobrevin (VAMP-8)	Synaptic System	104 303	1:200
Arp2 (B-6)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-376698	1:50
VARP (ANKRD27)	Origene	TA342941	1:50
SNAP23	Synaptic Systems	111-202	1:200
Stx11	Synaptic Systems	110-113	1:200
Phalloidin-iFluor 488 Reagent	Abcam	ab176753	1:3000
Phalloidin-iFluor 647 Reagent	Abcam	ab176759	1:3000
FM™ 1-43 Dye	ThermoFisher Sci.	T3163	10 µM
Secondary			
Alexa Fluor™-405-conjugated Goat anti-mouse	ThermoFisher Sci.	A-31553	1:400
Alexa Fluor™-647-conjugated Goat anti-mouse	ThermoFisher Sci.	A-21236	1:800
Alexa Fluor™-568-conjugated Goat anti-rabbit	ThermoFisher Sci.	A-11036	1:800
Cy™3 AffiniPure Donkey Anti-Goat IgG (H+L)	Jackson ImmunoResearch	705-165-147	1:200
Immunoprecipitation (IP) and western blot (WB)			
Primary			
β-actin (AC-15)	Merck	A5441	1:1000 (WB)
Abi-1 (B-12)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-271180	1:1000 (WB)
Arp3 (A-10)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-376625	1:1000 (WB)
Cdc42	Proteintech	10155-1-AP	1:1000 (WB)
Crk-L (C-20)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-319	1:1000 (WB)
C3G (G-4)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-17840	1:50 (IP) 1:1000 (WB)
C3G (C-19)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-869	1:50 (IP) 1:1000 (WB)
C3G (F-5)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-376992	1:1000 (WB)
Exo70 (D-6)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-365825	1:1000 (WB)
GFP (B-2)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-9996	1:1000 (WB)
HA	Abcam	ab137838	1:400 (IP) 1:2500 (WB)
HA.11 (16B12)	Covance	MMS-101R	1:50 (IP) 1:1000 (WB)
N-WASP (C-1)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-271484	1:1000 (WB)
Rac1	Cytoskeleton	ARC03	1:500 (WB)
RalA	Proteintech	67093-1-Ig	1:1000 (WB)
RhoA (67B9)	Cell Signalling	2117	1:1000 (WB)
Sec3/EXOC1	Proteintech	11690-1-AP	1:2000 (WB)
Sec5/EXOC2	Proteintech	12751-1-AP	1:2000 (WB)
Sec10 (C-4)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-514802	1:1000 (WB)
SNAP23	Synaptic Systems	111-202	1:50 (IP) 1:2000 (WB)
Stx11	Synaptic Systems	110-113	1:1000 (WB)
TI-VAMP (H-55) (VAMP-7)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-67060	1:1000 (WB)
Endobrevin (VAMP-8)	Synaptic System	104 303	1:1000 (WB)
WAVE2 (C-6)	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-373889	1:500 (WB)
Secondary			
Anti-Mouse IgG HRP-linked	GE HealthCare	NXA931	1:5000
Anti-Rabbit IgG HRP-linked	Santa Cruz Biotech.	sc-2004	1:5000
Anti-Mouse IgG Dylight 800	ThermoFisher Sci.	35521	1:5000
Anti-Mouse IgG Dylight 680	ThermoFisher Sci.	35518	1:5000
Anti-Rabbit IgG Dylight 680	ThermoFisher Sci.	35568	1:10000
Anti-Rabbit IgG Dylight 800	ThermoFisher Sci.	SA5-10036	1:10000
Anti-Goat AF680 IgG (H+L)	ThermoFisher Sci.	A-21084	1:10000

Supplemental Figure legends

Figure S1. C3G is not involved in granule biogenesis, δ -granule or lysosome exocytosis or endocytosis, but regulates VAMP-7 α -granule distribution. (A) Representative images of transmission electron microscopy of C3G-wt and C3G-KO platelets in steady-state conditions. Scale bar: 0.5 μ m. The green arrow indicates an α -granule, whereas the red arrow points to a δ -granule. (B) Bar graphs represent the quantification of the (left) platelet area, (middle) platelet perimeter, (right) platelet circularity. (C) Bar graphs represent the percentage of platelets (mean \pm SD) with more or less than 4 α -granules (left) or with 0, 1 or more than 2 δ -granules (right). (D) Line/scatter plots represent the mean \pm SD of VAMP-7 (upper) or VAMP-8 (lower) distribution along the platelet diameter (MFI) under resting conditions. (E) Platelets from wtC3G, tgC3G, C3G-wt and C3G-KO mice were stimulated with different concentrations of thrombin (TH) (0.2, 0.5 and 1 U/ml) for 20 min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. Platelet secretomes were mixed with the same volume of 5 mM 4-NAG (4-Nitrophenyl N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase) in Citrate Phosphate Buffer. β -hexosaminidase levels were measured by absorbance at 405 nm. The graph represents the percentage of hexosaminidase (mean \pm SD) released with respect to the total levels represented in F. (F) Quantification of total levels of β -hexosaminidase in resting tgC3G and C3G-KO platelets and their respective wild-types (mean \pm SD). a.u.: arbitrary units. (G) Washed blood from tgC3G, tgC3G Δ Cat, C3G-KO and their wild-type mice was stimulated with 2 mM Ca^{2+} and/or 0.5 U/ml thrombin (TH) and incubated with anti-CD63 antibody to monitor, by flow cytometry, the percentage of CD63 exposed on the platelet surface (mean \pm SD). (H) PRP from wtC3G, tgC3G, C3G-wt and C3G-KO mice was stimulated with thrombin (TH) (0.2, 0.5 or 1 U/ml) for 10 min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C, under stirring conditions. ATP levels in platelet secretomes were detected by bioluminescence using the CellTiter Glo 2.0 kit (mean \pm SD). (I) Representative images of tgC3G, tgC3G Δ Cat and C3G-KO platelets and their wild-types incubated with 5 μ M AF488-labeled fibrinogen (green) for different times (0, 5, 15 and 30 min) at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. Platelets were fixed and stained with phalloidin-iFluor 647 (red). Scale bar: 0.5 μ m. Line/scatter plots represent the quantification of the MFI (mean \pm SD) of AF488-fibrinogen endocytosed by platelets at the different times. AF: Alexa Fluor. (J) Washed blood from (left) wtC3G and tgC3G or (right) C3G-wt and C3G-KO mice was pre-treated with either (left) 1 μ M Go6976, 20 μ M PKC θ inhibitor or 100 μ M Vtx27 or (right) 2 μ M Go6976, 40 μ M PKC θ inhibitor or 200 μ M Vtx27 for 30 min or 5 μ M BIS for 5 min prior to stimulation with 1 U/ml thrombin (TH). Then blood was incubated with JON/A-PE antibody to monitor the percentage of platelets with active integrin α IIb β 3. Bar graphs represent the mean \pm SEM of the percentage of labeled platelets, normalized against the wild-type TH value. $\&\leq 0.05$, $\&\&\leq 0.001$ versus the corresponding wt; $\dagger p \leq 0.05$, $\dagger\dagger p \leq 0.01$, $\dagger\dagger\dagger p \leq 0.001$ versus thrombin-stimulated wild-type; $* p \leq 0.05$, $** p \leq 0.01$, $*** p \leq 0.001$ versus thrombin-stimulated tgC3G (left) or C3G-KO (right), respectively. MFI: Mean Fluorescence Intensity; a.u.: arbitrary units.

Figures S2. C3G regulates the interaction between v-SNARE and t-SNARE proteins during platelet exocytosis. (A) Lysates from HEK293T cells co-transfected with HA-C3G plus the indicated constructs, were immunoprecipitated with an anti-HA antibody and the levels of VAMP-7, VAMP-8, VARP, Sec3 and Exo70 were detected by WB, in the immunoprecipitates and in the total lysates, with anti-GFP antibodies. β -actin was monitored in the lysates as a loading control. (B) Representative immunofluorescence confocal microscopy images of C3G-wt and C3G-KO platelets stimulated with 0.2 U/ml thrombin for 1 min and spread

on poly-L-lysine for 30 min. Platelets were fixed and labeled with anti-VAMP-7 (158.2) + AF647 (red) and anti-Stx11 + AF568 (green). Scale bar: 2 μ m. Bar graphs show the Pearson's Correlation Coefficients (mean \pm SD) of the intensity values of VAMP-7 and Stx11. (C) Representative immunofluorescence confocal microscopy images of SNAP23-wt and SNAP23-KO platelets stimulated with 0.2 U/ml thrombin for 1 min and spread on poly-L-lysine or fibrinogen for 30 min. Platelets were fixed and labeled with phalloidin-iFluor 488 (green) and anti-C3G (G-4) + AF405 (blue), together with anti-VAMP-7 (H-55) + AF568 (red) (upper), anti-Stx11 + AF568 (red) (middle), or anti-VARP + AF568 (red) (lower). Scale bar: 2 μ m. Bar graphs show the Pearson's Correlation Coefficients (mean \pm SD) of (D) C3G and VAMP-7, (E) C3G and Stx11 and (F) C3G and VARP. * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$. Stx11: Syntaxin 11.

Figure S3. C3G regulates lamellipodia formation during spreading on specific substrates through GEF-dependent and -independent mechanisms. (A) Representative images of wtC3G Δ Cat and tgC3G Δ Cat platelets at rest or spread on poly-L-lysine, type I collagen, fibrinogen, fibronectin, laminin or vitronectin for 30 min after 0.2 U/ml thrombin stimulation for 1 min. Platelets were stained with phalloidin-iFluor 488 to visualize actin cytoskeleton. Scale bar: 5 μ m. Bar graphs represent the mean \pm SD of platelet area (μ m²). * $p \leq 0.05$. Substrates in which there are differences between genotypes are highlighted in red. a.u.: arbitrary units. (B) Washed blood from the indicated platelets was incubated with anti-GPVI-FITC and anti-CD61-PE, or anti-CD42b-PE and anti-CD41-APC antibodies for 15 min. Bar graphs represent the mean \pm SD of the MFI of GPVI, CD41, CD61 and CD42b levels on platelet surface. MFI: Mean Fluorescence Intensity. a.u.: arbitrary units. (C, D) Quantification of the different spreading phases in fixed platelets from (C) C3G-wt and C3G-KO or (D) wtC3G and tgC3G mice, after 5 and 15 min spreading on type I collagen, fibrinogen, fibronectin, laminin or vitronectin coated coverslips, induced by 0.2 U/ml thrombin for 1 min. Bar graphs represent the mean \pm SEM of the percentage of platelets in the different spreading phases: I: round platelets; II: platelets with filopodia; III: intermediate state with both filopodia and lamellipodia; IV: spread platelets. wt: wild-type; tg: transgenic; KO: knockout. (E) Representative images of wtC3G, tgC3G, C3G-wt and C3G-KO platelets spread for 30 min on poly-L-lysine coated coverslips after pre-treatment with 10 μ M PP2 for 2 min, 10 μ M cytochalasin (CytD) or 10 μ M latrunculin A (LatA) for 45 min, followed by stimulation with 0.2 U/ml thrombin (TH) for 1 min. Platelets were stained with phalloidin-iFluor 488 to visualize actin cytoskeleton. Scale bar: 5 μ m. Bar graphs represent the mean \pm SD of platelet area (μ m²). $\&\leq 0.05$, $\&\&\leq 0.01$, *versus* the corresponding wild-type; $\dagger\dagger p \leq 0.01$, $\dagger\dagger\dagger p \leq 0.001$ *versus* TH-induced wild-type spread platelets; * $p \leq 0.05$, *** $p \leq 0.001$ *versus* TH-stimulated tgC3G or C3G-KO spread platelets. (F) Lysates from HEK293T cells co-transfected with HA-C3G plus the indicated constructs, were immunoprecipitated with anti-HA antibodies. Arp3, Abi1, WASP1 and WAVE2 were detected by WB in the immunoprecipitates and in the total lysates with anti-GFP antibodies. VASP was detected with an anti-VASP antibody. β -actin was monitored in the lysates as a loading control.

Videos

Video 1. Spreading C3G-wt

https://drive.google.com/file/d/10TZ28Aluk3zHrQD58gjjciv2vDhhD4Qy/view?usp=share_link

Video 2. Spreading C3G-KO

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UI9NDneNQRupRjA_j7R7igH5Rfm42ho-/view?usp=share_link

Videos 1 and 2. C3G ablation delays platelet spreading. Videos showing the spreading of C3G-wt and C3G-KO platelets on ibiTreat plates. The sequential formation of filopodia and lamellipodia can be distinguished in C3G-wt platelets. C3G-KO platelets only show filopodia formation for the duration of the video. The videos summarize ~9 min of spreading. See [Fig. 3 A](#) for details.

Video 3. GFP

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IKPSjhn-cGkDk8cVTkRQNSF_gpfdC8xI/view?usp=share_link

Video 4. C3G-wt

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1u1-5NrKOGqo8JzyGgyCcB7hZpEU1P52v/view?usp=share_link

Video 5. C3G-Y554H

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xVrWUAX81JgG0eFhVwJGFA3AHWvJSRVE/view?usp=share_link

Videos 3-5. Effect of C3G hyperactivation on the kinetics of tdOrange-NPY release in PC12 cells. Videos showing the release of tdOrange-NPY vesicles from PC12 cells expressing GFP, C3G-wt or C3G-Y554H, after stimulation with KCl. The release of tdOrange-NPY is visualized by an increase in the fluorescence signal. The videos are slowed down to show the process of exocytosis that occurs in 12 seconds. See [Fig. 6 B and C](#) for details.

Video 6. shCT

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BNWVN_FSY4owBRn0gtD9ag4i3x2Pw05j/view?usp=share_link

Video 7. shC3G

https://drive.google.com/file/d/17tqj2QBIMZxVnSdjlZXp2bdmBL3LiW6N/view?usp=share_link

Videos 6 and 7. Effect of C3G silencing on the kinetics of tdOrange-NPY release in PC12 cells. Videos showing the release of tdOrange-NPY vesicles from PC12 cells expressing shCT and shC3G, after stimulation with KCl. The release of tdOrange-NPY is visualized by an increase in the fluorescence signal. The videos are slowed down to show the process of exocytosis that occurs in 12 seconds. See [Fig. 6 D and E](#) for details.

Video 8. shCT-VAMP-2

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Pq_CKsWFXHGx0zs6QWZH-oiQDpy2q8SU/view?usp=drivesdk

Video 9. shC3G-VAMP-2

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PlyEatiNGeBc9QopygLKa2sB1gyfhrXV/view?usp=sharing>

Videos 8 and 9. Effect of C3G silencing on the pore formation in PC12 cells. Videos showing the pore formation from single VAMP-2-pHmScarlet vesicle of PC12 cells expressing shCT and shC3G, after stimulation with KCl. The pore formation is visualized by a rapid increase in the fluorescence signal. The videos are slowed down to show the process of exocytosis that occurs in 8 seconds. See [Fig. 6 K](#) for details.

Figure S1

Figure S3